

Effects of Response Format and Number of Indicators on Results of Item Response Theory Models and Multivariate Techniques

Arimiyaw Zakaria (PhD), Ebenezer Apaflo* and Prof. Bismark Kwao Nkansah (PhD)

Department of Statistics, University of Cape Coast, Cape Coast, Ghana

***Corresponding author:** apafloeben69@gmail.com

Abstract

The determination of a standard test length that gives optimal statistical information about latent constructs with their dimensionality is a task that remains for investigation. In this regard, several datasets have been simulated under varied conditions of response scales, sets of items and dimensionality using the R package mirt. The data are examined using Item Response Theory (IRT) and compared with Factor Analysis output. The results show that IRT model fitness improves with increasing scale-points and higher dimensionality and generally with increasing set of variables. It is observed that on dichotomous scale in particular, higher number of items are suitable for measuring unidimensionality on lower point scale but could be misconstrued for bi-dimensionality. A higher measurement scale is found generally suitable to capture the appropriate underlying dimensionality. For both techniques, adequate model fitness is achieved with indicators not exceeding 40 in number.

Keywords: Item Response Theory, Measurement Scale, Response Format; Dimensionality Detection

1 Introduction

The goal of educational and psychological assessments is to determine an examinee's cognitive capacities and reflect them as a reliable numerical score by developing and giving a valid instrument (test) (Ogunsakin & Shogbesan, 2018). The type of instrument that yields easy analyzable responses is the multiple-choice (close-ended) tests, though many psychometricians establish that it is more difficult designing one than the subjective (open-ended) test. To many contemporary psychometricians, the length of an instrument that would be enough to measure sufficient statistical information about the intended latent ability is still a mirage.

The formulation of test items and proper test scoring are both topics covered by item response theory (IRT) (An & Yung, 2014). It is a group of measurement models that attempt to explain how one underlying construct and the observed item responses on a scale are related (Eleje, Onah, & Abanobi, 2018). IRT models use a non-linear monotonic function to describe the relationship between subjects' levels on a latent variable and the likelihood of a certain reaction to an item function (Eleje et al., 2018). IRT models express the association between an individual's response to an item and the underlying latent variable (ability) being measured by the instrument (questionnaire or test items) (Reeve, 2002).

On a multiple-choice examination, the response format and number of items, constitute a measurement scale. An example is a Likert scale item (usually in a questionnaire) which may have five response options, namely: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). A scale is a continuum made up of the highest point and the lowest point together with a number of intermediate points (thresholds) (Nkansah, Zakaria & Howard, 2019). The response structure for a multiple-choice test could either be dichotomous or polytomous. Scales are usually classified (Kothari, 2004; Desa & Latif, 2007) as unidimensional, measuring a single ability of the examinee, and multidimensional, involving more than one ability of the examinee.

It is critical to determine how real score estimates alter when item response calibrations differ in terms of their underlying dimensional structure (Wang, Harris, & Roussos, 2002). Thus, it may be of interest to identify the optimum number of dimensions in order to estimate quality characteristics, especially ability parameters. When it is unclear which model is accurate, adopting a multidimensional model is preferable to unidimensional one. Multidimensional models are advantageous of being able to differentiate amongst examinees more effectively (Ul Hassan & Miller, 2022).

One of the most used multivariate statistical methods for evaluating questionnaire or test items is factor analysis. According to Van der Eijk and Rose (2015), factor analysis (FA) accounts for the common variance among a set of items by their linear relationships to latent dimensions. Literature abounds on IRT with much concentration on model fit, estimation of item parameters using various estimation approaches, effect of sample size on scores, effects of scale type (response format) on results, differential item functioning, mixed scale types, and dimensionality detection and reduction. Notable among such studies is the work of Nkansah, Zakaria and Howard (2019), which examines the effect of measurement scales on the results of item response theory models and multivariate statistical techniques. The authors consider a fixed set of twenty items with varied sample sizes, and make recommendations on the number of points on response scales and sample size. In particular, a sample size of 150 is considered as optimal. However, a fixed set of twenty items in that study is quite restrictive. This means that further work in that regard is required on the standard test length that measures sufficient statistical information about the latent constructs which constitute what is referred to as the dimensionality of the resulting multivariate data. This paper attempts to address this gap, and establish the number of items/variables and response formats that are required to yield most optimal IRT results and factor solutions.

The remaining part of the paper is structured as follows: A brief overview of the methods is presented in Section 2. Section 3 reports the analysis and results of the study, and the discussion is subsequently provided in Section 4. Section 5 presents the conclusions.

2 Methods

This section briefly reviews the Item Response Theory and its relation to Factor Analysis (FA). It also describes the data generation mechanism.

2.1 Item Response Theory

By Item Response Theory, measurement models attempt to explain the connection between the observed item responses on a scale and an underlying construct (Eleje et al., 2018). Thus, the use of IRT models enables us to describe the association between subjects' levels on a latent variable (ability), measured by an instrument, and the probability of a positive response to an item, using a non-linear monotonic function (Eleje et al., 2018; Reeve, 2002).

The IRT models employed in the study are the two-parameter (2-PL), the multidimensional two-parameter (M2-PL), and the graded partial credit (GPC) model. In the 2PL model, for the unidimensional case, the probability of a positive response to an item is given by

$$P(X_{ij} = 1 | \theta, \alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[-1.702\alpha_i(\theta - \beta_i)]} \quad (4)$$

In this model, the probability of response to a dichotomous item is determined by the individual's ability level (θ), and two item parameters – discrimination (α) and the difficulty (β) parameter. The higher the value of α_i , the steeper the item characteristic curve, with values ranging over the interval (0, 2) inclusive.

The equivalence of Equation (4) in the multidimensional sense is the multidimensional two-parameter logistic (M2PL) model given by

$$P(X_{ij} = 1 | \theta_j, \alpha_i, \mathbf{d}_i) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[-1.702(\alpha_i' \theta_j + \mathbf{d}_i)]} \quad (5)$$

where, α_i is a vector of discrimination parameters for item i , and $\mathbf{d}_i = \mathbf{1}'\alpha_i\beta_i$ is a scalar parameter related to the item difficulty.

For polytomous items, we consider the GPC model, which also applies 2PL concept to ordered categorical responses (Matlock, Turner, & Gitche, 2018). It allows varying discrimination parameters across items (Swaminathan, Hambleton, & Rogers, 2006), and the probability of observing a response in category g over category $(g - 1)$ for item i is given by (Muraki, 1992)

$$P(X_i = g | \theta, \alpha_i, \beta_{ih}) = \frac{\exp\left[\sum_{h=0}^g \alpha_h(\theta - \beta_{ih})\right]}{\sum_{k=0}^{n_i} \exp\left[\sum_{h=0}^k \alpha_h(\theta - \beta_{ih})\right]} \quad (6)$$

where α_h denotes the discrimination associated with response category h on item i .

In IRT, item characteristics curve (ICC) is often used to display a person's probability of response, $P(\theta)$, to an item as well as their level θ on the scale's construct (Edelen & Reeve, 2007). Thus, the ICC reveals information about the chances of persons of given trait level successfully answering any item (Furr & Bacharach, 2013).

Another useful graphical tool IRT is the item information function/curve (IIF), which shows the amount of information that can be obtained from the item along the trait continuum. By accumulating the IIFs for different items measuring a latent construct to obtain the test information function (TIF) (Reise & Waller, 2009), the TIF then indicates how well each ability level is being estimated by the test (Thorpe & Favia, 2012). The item information, $I_i(\theta)$, is obtained by expressing the Fisher's information as a function of ability parameter θ . For the 2PL model, the IIF is given by

$$I_i(\theta) = \alpha_i^2 P_i(\theta) [1 - P_i(\theta)]$$

with the corresponding TIF given as

$$I(\theta) = \sum_i \alpha_i^2 P_i(\theta) [1 - P_i(\theta)]$$

Since the IIF curve is often symmetric about the value of the item difficulty parameter, there is indication that any item that fits the 2PL model is most informative for persons whose abilities match the difficulty of the item. As ability becomes either less or greater than the item difficulty, the item information decreases. An item that has higher information has the capability to discriminate between individuals with different levels of agreeability (θ) on the item (Raju, Su, & Patrician, 2014). Generally, therefore, the instrument provides greater information at an average ability level, but provides less information at higher ability levels.

2.2 Factor Analysis Technique

Factor analysis technique estimates the relationships between items and latent traits by means of correlation (Kořar, 2018). These factors are thought to reflect underlying processes that have created the correlations among the variables (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). A one-factor model expresses the relationship between the underlying factor θ , and the continuous indicator variable Y_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$. Thus,

$$Y_i = \lambda_i \theta + \varepsilon_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p \tag{7}$$

where, λ_i is the loading of Y_i on θ .

For a multiple m -factor model for a homogenous population with mean vector, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$, the equivalence of Equation (7) in matrix notation form becomes

$$\mathbf{y} = \boldsymbol{\Lambda}\boldsymbol{\theta} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \tag{8}$$

where $\mathbf{y} = (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_p)'$, $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_m)'$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_p)'$ and Λ is an $(m \times p)$ matrix of loadings. Based on the usual assumptions:

$$E(\mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{0}_{(p \times 1)}, \quad E(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{0}_{(m \times 1)}, \quad \text{var}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{I}_{(m \times m)}, \quad E(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{0}_{(p \times 1)}$$

$$\text{cov}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \text{diag}(\psi_1, \psi_2, \dots, \psi_p), \quad \text{and} \quad \text{cov}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{0}_{(p \times m)},$$

the variance-covariance matrix of the observed variables, Σ , may be expressed in terms of the factor loadings and the unique factors as

$$\Sigma = \Lambda\Lambda' + \Psi \tag{9}$$

Thus, the variance Y_i is partitioned into one due to common factors (i.e, the communality) and specific variances, ψ_i . The covariances of the Y 's with the θ 's can be found in terms of λ 's, and given as $\text{cov}(\mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \Lambda$. The item-factor relations have been clearly established (Nkansah et al., 2019).

3 Data Description

For thorough investigation of the effect of response scale and number of indicators (or indicator dimensionality) on the results of IRT and factor analysis, seventy-four datasets have been simulated under varied response scales and different sets of items and underlying dimensionality using the R package *mirt* (Chalmers, 2012). Datasets are generated for both dichotomous and polychotomous cases. For the polychotomous case, data is generated for three-point, five-point and seven- point response scales. Based on Nkansah et al. (2019), an optimal sample size of 200 is obtained for responses generated for all response scales under different sets of variables (items): 15, 20, 30, 40, 45 and 50 items. Further, various dimensions, namely unidimensional, two-dimensions and three-dimensions of latent person-ability are considered for each response scale. Based on the assumption that items have different discrimination powers, 2PL model is used to simulate unidimensional dichotomous datasets. In the case of multidimensional dichotomous datasets, the multidimensional two-parameter logistic (M2PL) IRT model is employed. The generalized partial credit (GPC) model is used for the simulation of both unidimensional and multidimensional polytomous item response datasets.

4 Analysis and Results

This section presents the analyses and results of simulated datasets using the R packages *mirt*, for IRT, and *psych*, in the case of factor analysis. In the IRT paradigm, the analyses of unidimensional dichotomous item response datasets are based on two-parameter logistic (2PL) IRT model, whereas multidimensional two-parameter logistic (M2PL) IRT model is employed in the analyses of multidimensional dichotomous datasets. For unidimensional polytomous item response datasets, we employ the generalised partial credit (GPC) model in the analyses. In terms of multidimensional polytomous datasets, the multidimensional generalized partial credit (MGPC) model is used to conduct the analyses.

Factor analyses of dichotomous item response datasets are based on tetrachoric correlation matrices. The polychoric correlation matrix is rather used as input in factor analysis of polytomous item response datasets.

4.1 IRT results across different measurement scales on various dimensions

The quality of measurement instruments is usually assessed through test information curve (TIC), which indicates the amount of statistical information measured by the instrument.

Figure 1 displays the TICs for various sets of items on unidimensional dichotomous scales.

(c) Set of 30 items

(d) Set of 40 items

(e) Set of 45 items

(f) Set of 50 items

Figure 1: TICs for various sets of items on unidimensional dichotomous scales

It is clear that all the curves (1a to 1f) exhibit bimodal distributions. It is also observed that there is marginal improvement in the area under the curves with increasing sets of variables and test information. The test information measured by the unidimensional dichotomous scale spans between 5 and about 18 with the highest achieved at set of 45 variables. The bimodality of the distributions shows that there could in reality be two underlying dimensions exhibited by the variables even though unidimensionality is initially assumed.

The TICs for different sets of items on two-dimensional dichotomous scale are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: TICs for different sets of items on two-dimensional dichotomous scale

In Figure 2, it is seen that the shape of the surface becomes more uniformly broad for 20 set of variables (Fig. 2b). This means that information is quite fairly represented in the data covered by 20 items for almost all levels of two underlying dimensions, even though the amount of information achieved could be quite low. However, the optimal information is derived from the data at average levels (origin) of the two dimensions at sets of high number of variables. Figures 1 and 2 therefore show that even if a single dimension is assumed in the generation of the data on a two-point scale, two dimensions are more likely to be identified, and the greatest amount of information is achieved at average levels of the two dimensions

(capabilities) at high numbers of indicators. Figures 2 (a) – (f) broadens as the test information increases with increasing sets of variables. In the two-dimensional dichotomous surfaces, the test information measured ranges from 7 to about 40, the highest achieved at set of 45 items.

On the three-point scale, the TICs for various sets of items with underlying unidimensionality are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: TICs for sets of items with underlying unidimensionality measured on three-point scale

It is clear that for all sets of items (Fig. 3a - 3f), the TICs exhibit similar shapes but with increasing area as number of items increases. The test information measured from the graphs ranges from 21.3 to 78.5, with the highest achieved at set of 45 items. The amounts of information are obviously higher than those captured under the two-point scale. The shape also shows that unidimensionality is well depicted over three-point scale as the graphs exhibit single peak.

The TICs under three-point scale for various sets of items are plotted against possible underlying two-dimensional traits, and presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: TICs for various sets of items with underlying two-dimensions measured on three-point scale

The two-dimensional three-point scale surfaces depict similar shapes but more refined than those of the two-dimensional dichotomous scales and with higher test information (from about 25 to about 95) with increasing numbers of items, the highest achieved at set of 45 items. Throughout the cases, the highest information is obtained for average levels of one dimension and higher levels of the other dimension.

The IRT results are assessed across number of points on response scales, number of items and number of dimensions of person abilities. Table 1 illustrates summary statistics for IRT results across different response scales under various dimensions. The table is examined for general features and those specific to the dimensionality.

Table 1: Summary statistics of IRT results for all measurement scales under various dimensions and different sets of variables

Scale	Dimensions	Measures	Sets of Items					
			15	20	30	40	45	50
Two-point	Unidim.	Fit items	14	20	27	40	44	49
		Model fit	0.059	0.147	0.778	0.895	0.579	0.146
	Two-dim.	Fit items	14	18	30	39	42	47
		Model fit	0.088	0.091	0.115	0.324	0.129	0.188
	Three-dim.	Fit items	10	17	30	34	30	43
		Model fit	0.054	0.009	0.177	0.021	0.000	0.000
Three-point	Unidim.	Fit items	12	18	30	39	43	49
		Model fit	0.290	0.259	0.625	0.053	0.062	0.122
	Two-dim.	Fit items	15	20	29	40	35	29
		Model fit	0.453	0.247	0.323	0.234	0.000	0.000
	Three-dim.	Fit items	14	19	29	39	42	46
		Model fit	0.253	0.291	0.794	0.227	0.429	0.763
Five-point	Unidim.	Fit items	13	18	27	36	38	45
		Model fit	0.743	0.175	0.583	0.022	0.168	0.195
	Two-dim.	Fit items	11	18	30	34	42	48
		Model fit	0.345	0.048	0.557	0.798	0.725	0.846
	Three-dim.	Fit items	15	20	30	36	42	31
		Model fit	0.125	0.324	0.337	0.539	0.994	0.996
Seven-point	Unidim.	Fit items	15	18	26	28	38	40
		Model fit	0.277	0.036	0.000	0.419	0.181	0.422
	Two-dim.	Fit items	13	18	22	38	42	38
		Model fit	0.071	0.113	0.864	0.988	0.996	0.999
	Three-dim.	Fit items	10	14	15	31	28	27
		Model fit	0.795	0.815	0.951	0.985	0.355	0.000

Table 1 shows that the number of fit items improves as the number of items increases for all scale points and dimensionality except for the seven-point scale, where the number of fit items experience a marginal drop for the higher sets (45 and 50) of items under higher dimensions of the latent construct. However, for two-point scale, model fitness deteriorates after set of 40 items. It is clear that on this scale, it is a single dimension that could be suitably measured. For three-point scale, model fitness deteriorates after set of 30 items, and multiple

dimensionality could be suitably measured on this scale for these sets of items. For higher point scales (5 and 7), model fitness appears optimal at set of 40 items and suitable for measuring higher dimensionality rather than single dimension.

Table 1 further shows that unidimensionality could be effectively fitted with smaller number (15) of items on higher-point scale, but with larger number (30 –40) on lower-point scale.

The box plot in Figure 5 is used to summarize the IRT model fitness for different sets of items filtered from Table 1 across all dimensionalities.

Figure 5: Box plot of IRT model fitness for various sets of variables.

From Figure 5, there is a general fluctuation in the fitness of the IRT models with increasing sets of variables. The lowest level of fit variation is produced in 20-item dataset. The single outlier observed in this case is the fit for a three-dimensional model on a seven-point scale observed on 20-item data in Table 1. This shows that it is an exceptional case to achieve a high model fit for low-dimensional data (i.e., on few variables) with rather high number of underlying dimensionalities, but which is achieved on a high-point scale. This observation is also true for similar data structure on 15 items.

4.2 Factor analysis results from various measurement scales

In this sub-section, we compare summary of factor analysis results from various measurement scales and dimensionalities for different sets of variables. Table 2 shows the summary statistics of factor solutions for various sets of variables.

Table 2: Summary statistics of factor solutions for sets of indicators on various scales

Scale	Factors	Measures	Sets of Indicators					
			15	20	30	40	45	50
Two-point	One	Cum. Var.	0.307	0.289	0.297	0.283	0.287	0.278
		Model fit	0.710	0.716	0.787	0.793	0.805	0.801
	Two	Cum. Var.	0.575	0.578	0.548	0.538	0.544	0.551
		Model fit	0.904	0.924	0.927	0.936	0.939	0.948
	Three	Cum. Var.	0.628	0.594	0.570	0.540	0.535	0.544
		Model fit	0.920	0.911	0.922	0.922	0.921	0.931
Three-point	One	Cum. Var.	0.403	0.384	0.398	0.388	0.394	0.383
		Model fit	0.844	0.857	0.901	0.911	0.920	0.920
	Two	Cum. Var.	0.698	0.714	0.709	0.692	0.696	0.702
		Model fit	0.975	0.982	0.986	0.986	0.987	0.988
	Three	Cum. Var.	0.711	0.710	0.704	0.704	0.703	0.704
		Model fit	0.972	0.977	0.981	0.984	0.985	0.986
Five-point	One	Cum. Var.	0.510	0.494	0.512	0.499	0.503	0.485
		Model fit	0.917	0.928	0.954	0.959	0.963	0.961
	Two	Cum. Var.	0.827	0.838	0.836	0.821	0.824	0.826
		Model fit	0.994	0.996	0.997	0.996	0.997	0.997
	Three	Cum. Var.	0.842	0.840	0.829	0.830	0.831	0.828
		Model fit	0.993	0.994	0.995	0.996	0.996	0.996
Seven point	One	Cum. Var.	0.595	0.585	0.608	0.499	0.582	0.564
		Model fit	0.950	0.959	0.975	0.979	0.978	0.976
	Two	Cum. Var.	0.888	0.897	0.892	0.879	0.885	0.886
		Model fit	0.997	0.998	0.999	0.998	0.999	0.999
	Three	Cum. Var.	0.897	0.895	0.892	0.890	0.889	0.886
		Model fit	0.997	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998

Table 2 shows that all possible factor solutions would be significant on all scale-points and that model fitness for a given solution improves with increasing scale points. However, model performance does not markedly improve with increasing number of items. It is noteworthy that on two-point scale, the cumulative variation explained is generally at the peak at set of 15 or 20 variables for all factor solutions. This observation is generally true for all other scale points.

The box plot in Figure 6 is filtered from Table 2 to summarize the variation in the cumulative variance accounted for by all the three factor solutions under the different sets of variables.

Figure 6: Box plot of cumulative variances of the three factors for sets of variables.

Figure 6 shows that the performance of the factor models is not too sensitive to the number of indicator variables; differences in their H-spreads, medians, lower and upper quartiles are negligible. This observation may be seen from Table 2.

4.3 Discussion

The results shows that the effect of measurement sales and number of indicators on dimensionality detection in multivariate data is more clearly demonstrated by IRT. However, the significance of the model fitness is better highlighted with Factor Analysis. Unlike many psychometric literature, (e.g., Eijk & Rose, 2015), it is evident in this study that, under various conditions, detecting dimensionality is clearly reflected under IRT rather than Factor Analysis. The finding could be rather in line with the general assertion in psychometric literature and confirmed by Choi and Bachman (1992), that model misfit has a strong correlation with violation of the unidimensional assumption, which is consistent with IRT. It is demonstrated in this paper that extraction of unidimensionality could be quite elusive.

The general fluctuation in the fitness of the IRT models with increasing sets of variables is in consonance with Bock and Haberman (2009) who assert that large datasets have significant levels of misfit.

Though the fixed set of 20 items selected for the study in Nkansah et al. (2019) is basically for convenience, this study has provided the implications for using this set of items. It is observed that lower set of indicators like 20 are particularly adequate for capturing the optimal performance of factor solutions on all scale points, and unidimensionality on higher-point scale in IRT. Effect of scale-type is however not seen clearly in results of IRT models with this set of items.

5 Conclusions

The study highlights the sensitivity of the IRT in determining the performance of dimensionality detection in the presence of varied conditions of measurement scales and number of indicators. However, Factor Analysis is likely to produce significant models for all conditions considered although with varied model fitness. On both techniques, adequate model fitness is achieved with indicators not exceeding 40 in number.

Unidimensionality is effectively fitted with smaller number (15) of items on higher-point scale, but with larger number (30 –40) on lower-point scale. Higher dimensionality is rather measured adequately on higher scale points with higher number of indicators.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors' Contributions

All the authors contributed significantly in writing this article. The authors read and approved the final manuscript.

References

- An, X., & Yung, Y. F. (2014). Item response theory: What it is and how you can use the IRT procedure to apply it. *SAS Institute Inc. SAS364-2014, 10(4)*, 1-14.
- Bock, R. D., & Haberman, S. J. (2009). Confidence bands for examining goodness-of-fit of estimated item response functions. In *annual meeting of the Psychometric Society, Cambridge, UK*.
- Caragay, K. T. (2015). *Using Polytomous Item Response Analysis in Constructing a Career Themes Inventory for Filipino High School Students* (Doctoral dissertation, University of the Philippines-Diliman).

Received: 2 November 2024

Revised: 12 November 2024

Accepted: 16 November 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14172837](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14172837)

- Chalmers, R. P. (2012). mirt: A multidimensional item response theory package for the R environment. *Journal of statistical Software*, 48, 1-29.
- Choi, I. C., & Bachman, L. F. (1992). An investigation into the adequacy of three IRT models for data from two EFL reading tests. *Language Testing*, 9(1), 51-78.
- DeCoster, J. (1998). Overview of Factor Analysis. Retrieved November 22, 2023 from <http://www.stat-help.com/notes.html>
- Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). *Fundamentals of Research Writing and Uses of Research Methodologies*. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Desa, Z. N. D. M., & Latif, A. (2007). Probability Theory and Application of Item Response Theory. In *Kertas dibenrtangkan di 1st International Malaysian Educational Technology Convention, Sofitel Palm Resort, Senai, Malaysia, 2nd–5th November*.
- Edelen, M. O., & Reeve, B. B. (2007). Applying item response theory (IRT) modeling to questionnaire development, evaluation, and refinement. *Quality of life research*, 16, 5-18.
- Eleje, L. I., Onah, F. E., & Abanobi, C. C. (2018). *Comparative study of classical test theory and item response theory using diagnostic quantitative economics skill test item analysis results*. *European Journal of Educational and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 71 – 89.
- Frey, B. B. (Ed.). (2018). *The SAGE encyclopedia of educational research, measurement, and evaluation*. California, CA: Sage Publications.
- Furr, R. M., & Bacharach, V. R. (2013). *Psychometrics: An Introduction* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Koğar, H. (2018). Effects of Various Simulation Conditions on Latent-Trait Estimates: A Simulation Study. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 5(2), 263-273.
- Kothari, R. C. (2004). *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques* (3rd ed.). New Delhi, India: New Age International.
- Matlock, K. L., Turner, R. C., & Gitche, W. D. (2018). A study of reverse-worded matched item pairs using the generalized partial credit and nominal response models. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 78(1), 103-127.
- Muraki, E. (1992). A generalized partial credit model: Application of an EM algorithm. *Applied psychological measurement*, 16(2), 159-176.
- Nkansah, B. K., Zakaria, A., & Howard, N. K. (2019). *Effect of Measurement Scales on Results*

- of Item Response Theory Models and Multivariate Statistical Techniques*. Journal of Informatics and Mathematical Sciences, 11(1), 51–79.
- Nor, Z., Desa, D., & Latif, A. A. (n.d.). *Probability Theory and Application of Item Response Theory*. Educational Technology, 703–711.
- Ogunsakin, I. B., & Shogbesan, Y. O. (2018). Item response theory (IRT): a modern statistical theory for solving measurement problem in 21st century. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 11, 627-635.
- Ostini, R., & Nering, M. L. (2006). *Polytomous item response theory models*. California, CA: Sage Publications.
- Raju, D., Su, X., & Patrician, P. A. (2014). Using item response theory models to evaluate the practice environment scale. *Journal of Nursing Measurement*, 22(2), 323-341.
- Reeve, B. B. (2002). An introduction to modern measurement theory. *National Cancer Institute*, 1-67.
- Reise, S. P., & Waller, N. G. (2009). Item response theory and clinical measurement. *Annual review of clinical psychology*, 5, 27-48.
- Swaminathan, H., Hambleton, R. K., & Rogers, H. J. (2006). 21 Assessing the Fit of Item Response Theory Models. *Handbook of statistics*, 26, 683-718.
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2013). *Using multivariate statistics* (6th ed.). New Jersey, NJ: Pearson Education.
- Thorpe, G. L., & Favia, A. (2012). Data Analysis Using Item Response Theory Methodology: An Introduction to Selected Programs and Applications. *Psychology Faculty Scholarship*.20. Retrieved from https://digitalcommons.library.umaine.edu/psy_facpub/20/
- Ul Hassan, M., & Miller, F. (2022). Discrimination with unidimensional and multidimensional item response theory models for educational data. *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation*, 51(6), 2992-3012.
- Van der Eijk, C., & Rose, J. (2015). Risky business: factor analysis of survey data—assessing the probability of incorrect dimensionalisation. *PloS one*, 10(3), e0118900.
- Wang, X. B., Harris, V., & Roussos, L. (2002). Effects of Multidimensionality on IRT Item Characteristics and True Score Estimates: Implications for Computerized Test Assembly. Computerized Testing Report. LSAC Research Report Series.